

THE P'URHÉPECHA SELF-GOVERNMENT OF CHERÁN AND COMMUNITY RESPONSES TO THE PANDEMIC

ANTONIO FUENTES DÍAZ

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This text is a revised English edition of an article originally published in Spanish in 2020. The present version includes minor stylistic revisions and a new introductory note situating the article within subsequent debates on Indigenous autonomy and self-government in Mexico.

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ABSTRACT: This article analyzes the response to Covid-19 in the P'urhépecha community of San Francisco Cherán, Michoacán, Mexico. It argues that this response was shaped through the practices and institutions that emerged from the struggle for collective rights, self-determination, and self-government initiated in 2011 in the context of defending the communal forest against illegal logging facilitated by collusion between government authorities and organized crime. Long-standing communal health memories are intertwined with contemporary strategies to confront Covid-19 through the use of traditional medicine and midwifery, combined with hygiene measures and clinical health monitoring.

Keywords: Indigenous autonomy; community governance; community care; decolonial studies; legal pluralism

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Introduction to the English Translation

This paper presents an English translation and revised edition of an article originally published in 2020. At the time, the authors were conducting fieldwork in Cherán and other P'urhépecha communities when the Covid-19 pandemic abruptly transformed the social and political landscape. Like many researchers, we were compelled to reconsider our research objectives in order to document the strategies, challenges, and responses that emerged within these communities as they confronted the health emergency.

The original article sought to offer a multidisciplinary perspective on the pandemic by recognizing the difficulties faced by the community while also making visible the diverse forms of collective action developed by different sectors of local society. Beyond its immediate relevance to the Covid-19 context, I believe the case remains significant because it illustrates the tensions and articulations between communal governing institutions, state institutions, and other actors within the community. The pandemic made these relationships especially visible, but the underlying dynamics extend far beyond that particular historical moment.

The case has acquired renewed relevance in light of recent legal and political developments in Mexico. In 2024, constitutional reforms formally recognized Indigenous and Afro-Mexican communities as subjects of public law, expanding the possibilities for communities to exercise self-government and directly administer public resources. This reform has been widely interpreted as opening new institutional pathways for Indigenous self-determination, drawing attention to experiences such as that of Cherán.

At the same time, these developments have generated important academic and political debates. Some scholars have questioned whether models based primarily on the direct allocation and administration of public budgets should be understood as expressions of autonomy. On the one hand, the management of public resources requires compliance with legal, administrative, and financial regulations that may limit the ability of communities to govern according to their own traditions and normative systems. On the other hand, institutional recognition can obscure the broader challenges posed by

predatory capitalism, extractivism, and ongoing processes of territorial dispossession.

As the present article suggests, Indigenous communities exercise multiple forms of autonomy that are not always articulated with one another and may even enter into tension with communal institutions themselves, rather than only with state institutions. For this reason, autonomous movements should be understood in their complexity, taking into account their capacity for collective agency, their memories of struggle and resistance, and their ability to generate new forms of political agreement and communal organization.

More than a study of pandemic governance, this article offers a window into the diverse ways in which autonomy is practiced, negotiated, and reimagined within Indigenous communities confronting multiple and overlapping challenges.

I. Colonialism, Territorial Conflict, and Indigenous Emergence

During the 1990s, a wave of Indigenous mobilizations emerged across much of Latin America. As collective political subjects, these movements articulated specific demands for self-determination and autonomy. The rise of Indigenous movements must be understood within the broader shift toward neoliberal globalization that began in the mid-1980s with the implementation of the so-called *Washington Consensus*.¹ In Mexico, neoliberal policies began with the country's incorporation into the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade (GATT) in 1986 and deepened with the entry into force of the North American Free Trade Agreement (NAFTA) in 1994.

This transformation of the development model intensified the long-standing chain of exclusion affecting those who lacked capital, technology, industrial production knowledge, and commercial networks necessary to compete with transnational corporations and producers operating within the framework of an open-market economy.² Sustained largely through extractive-export models, this transformation heightened tensions between Indigenous peoples and nation-states, since many national biotic resources are located within communal or ejidal territories inhabited by Indigenous communities.³

From the beginning of neoliberalism, diverse social sectors opposed this model. Within these forms of resistance, Indigenous mobilizations stood out for challenging their

¹ These measures essentially consisted in reducing public spending, with significant cuts to resources allocated to social welfare, in order to redirect investment toward sectors capable of generating immediate economic returns. In addition, state-owned enterprises, public resources, and public services were to be privatized; a legal system guaranteeing property rights was to be established; incentives to promote foreign investment were to be created; and any regulations hindering free competition between international corporations and domestic companies were to be eliminated. See John Williamson, "Revisión del consenso de Washington", in Louis Emmerij y Jose Núñez (eds.), *El desarrollo económico y social en los umbrales del siglo XXI*, BID. Washington D.C., 1998.

² Humberto González, "Convergencia: movimientos sociales en la era de globalización neoliberal, in Gerardo Otero (coord.), *México en transición, globalismo neoliberal, Estado y sociedad civil*, H. Cámara de diputados, LIX legislatura, Simon Fraser University, Universidad Autónoma de Zacatecas, Miguel Ángel Porrúa. México, 2006.

³ Carlos Lucio, *Conflictos socioambientales, derechos humanos y movimiento indígena en el Istmo de Tehuantepec*, Universidad Autónoma de Zacatecas. México, 2016.

historically unequal incorporation into the nation-state—further intensified by economic globalization. In this context, these movements advocated for the creation of a multiethnic and pluricultural state capable not only of recognizing differentiated identities, but also of dismantling the structural conditions of domination and subordination through which Indigenous peoples had been integrated into previous development models.⁴ Another central demand concerned the recognition of Indigenous peoples as subjects of public law rather than merely entities of “public interest,” as well as their incorporation into the state through self-determination and autonomy.⁵

During the 1990s, these mobilizations, together with the ratification of ILO Convention 169, triggered a wave of constitutional and legal reforms throughout Latin America.⁶ However, constitutional reforms in Mexico remained limited regarding the recognition of Indigenous peoples and communities as subjects of public law. These legal limitations contributed to the emergence of *de facto autonomías*, the most emblematic example being the declaration of autonomous municipalities in Chiapas by the Zapatista Army of National Liberation (EZLN). These struggles were aimed at securing the right to autonomy and other collective rights, but no longer primarily through constitutional recognition; rather, autonomy was constructed through everyday practice and lived political experience.⁷

For Lucio,⁸ one of the major obstacles to the full recognition of Indigenous rights lies in development models that continue reproducing forms of dispossession and subordination, thereby intensifying tensions between the state and Indigenous peoples. Consequently, he

⁴ Francisco López Bárcenas, *Autonomías y Derechos Indígenas en México*, Miguel Carranza Editores, Centro de Orientación y Asesoría a Pueblos Indígenas, 5th edition, México, 2005.

⁵ Marco Aparicio, “El Derecho de Los Pueblos Indígenas a La Libre Determinación”, in *Pueblos Indígenas y Derechos Humanos*, Universidad de Deusto. Bilbao, 2006.

⁶ Raquel Yrigoyen, “Hitos Del Reconocimiento Del Pluralismo Jurídico y El Derecho Indígena En Las Políticas Indigenistas y El Constitucionalismo Andino”, in *Pueblos Indígenas y Derechos Humanos*, Universidad de Deusto. Bilbao, 2006.

⁷ Francisco López, “Los Movimientos Indígenas En México: Rostros y Caminos”, en *El Cotidiano*. 2016; Marco Aparicio, “El Derecho de Los Pueblos Indígenas a La Libre Determinación”, in *Pueblos Indígenas y Derechos Humanos*, Universidad de Deusto. Bilbao, 2006.

⁸ Carlos Lucio, *Conflictos socioambientales...* cit.

proposes examining the dominance of development policies through the framework of internal colonialism. According to sociologist Silvia Rivera,⁹ internal colonialism can be understood as a set of diachronic contradictions of varying depth that emerge on the surface of contemporaneity and thus traverse the coexisting spheres of modes of production, state political systems, and ideologies anchored in cultural homogeneity.

Although Rivera developed these ideas primarily in relation to Bolivia, she argues that they may also be applicable to other non-Western societies characterized by heterogeneous social compositions. Her central working hypothesis is that contemporary society continues to operate through forms of domination sustained by a long-standing colonial horizon, to which more recent cycles of liberalism and populism have become articulated without fully overcoming or transforming colonial structures. These more recent political horizons have merely refunctionalized long-standing colonial structures, converting them into modalities of internal colonialism that remain crucial for explaining social stratification, political exclusion, and structural violence. For Rivera, the political cycles that followed formal colonialism—such as liberal republics and national states—reproduced historical structures of inequality imposed upon Indigenous populations.¹⁰

At the same time, these development projects established forms of discrimination grounded in doctrines such as social Darwinism during the liberal period and assimilationist ideologies centered on mestizaje throughout the twentieth century. Nevertheless, these successive horizons—colonial, liberal, nationalist, and neoliberal—have also been challenged and negotiated by Indigenous resistance movements, which have emerged in recent decades as significant political subjects.

Socio-environmental conflicts and organized crime

One of the main factors challenging dominant development paradigms has been the environmental destruction generated by industrialization and extractivist models

⁹ Silvia Rivera, *Violencias (re) encubiertas*, La mirada salvaje/Editorial Piedra Rota. Bolivia, 2010.

¹⁰ Ídem

implemented throughout the global periphery. In recent decades, Latin America has witnessed the proliferation of projects focused on the exploitation of natural resources, resulting in the expansion of extractive industries and agro-industrial production primarily directed toward global commodity markets. This growing emphasis on extractivism has generated socio-environmental resistance movements. Struggles for land and labor rights characteristic of twentieth-century peasant and working-class movements have increasingly shifted toward resistance against the extraction of common goods by mining projects, tourism developments, urban expansion, and hydroelectric projects, since these initiatives threaten not only material livelihoods but also forms of social organization and ways of life.

Between January 2009 and December 2013, more than 160 socio-environmental conflicts were documented in Mexico.¹¹ In many of these cases, territorial defense became central, incorporating both environmental and ethno-territorial dimensions. The emphasis on territory is significant because territory constitutes a symbolic system and a culturally specific way of inhabiting and giving meaning to space.¹² Territory emerges from multiple antagonistic interactions that shape it as a site of defense against state projects, private investment, and criminal economic powers.

In recent decades, organized crime has acquired a particularly important role in these territorial conflicts, diversifying its activities beyond drug trafficking toward extortion and the control of highly profitable agricultural markets. In Michoacán, criminal organizations have taken advantage of export-oriented agricultural economies centered on products such as avocados, berries, and citrus fruits. Another especially profitable form of organized criminal activity has been illegal logging.

Socio-environmental resistance movements organized by Indigenous peoples and local

¹¹ Maria Paz, “Luchas en defensa del territorio. reflexiones desde los conflictos socio ambientales en México”, in *Acta Sociológica*, no. 73, 2017, p. 197-219.

¹² Alicia Barabas, “La construcción de etnoterritorios en las culturas indígenas de Oaxaca”, in *Desacatos*, no. 14, 2004, p. 145-168. José Seoane, “Movimientos sociales y recursos naturales en América Latina: resistencias al neoliberalismo, configuración de alternativas”, en *Sociedade e Estado*, vol. 21, núm. 1, 2006, p. 85-107.

communities can therefore be understood as coordinated forms of defense against the destructive effects of capital accumulation, state power, and criminal violence, insofar as these forces also threaten the symbolic systems through which communities inhabit and reproduce themselves culturally. A paradigmatic example of territorial defense against criminal actors occurred in the Indigenous community of San Francisco Cherán, Michoacán, in April 2011.¹³ This event triggered processes of community self-defense, self-determination, and self-government.

II. Autonomy and the Uses of Law in Cherán.

During the early morning of April 15, 2011, a group of women accompanied by young people initiated a mobilization against trucks transporting illegally logged timber protected by logging entrepreneurs and armed members of organized crime. After intercepting the trucks and detaining several loggers, they launched fireworks and rang the bells of the Calvario church to alert the inhabitants of the town. In what participants later described as an “instinctive” response, residents carried stones to the church and erected barricades at the five entrances to the town in order to prevent further incursions by criminal groups. The municipal president fled, and municipal police officers were disarmed because of their complicity with organized crime.

This initial reactive phase, known as “the uprising,” during which the community effectively self-besieged, was followed by the construction of an ethno-political movement and a community-based security structure organized around three demands: the protection of life, justice for murdered and disappeared community members, and the restoration of the forests. During the first days of the uprising, collective decisions focused on

¹³ The municipality of San Francisco Cherán is located in the heart of the P’urhépecha Plateau in the state of Michoacán. Its territory covers approximately 222.8 square kilometers and has a population of 18,141 inhabitants. The municipal seat of Cherán concentrates 78% of the population. SEDESOL, *Catálogo de Localidades*, available at <http://www.microrregiones.gob.mx/catloc/LocdeMun.aspx?tipo=clave&campo=loc&ent=16&mun=024> [last accessed: April 10, 2020].

immediate survival strategies. However, these experiences profoundly transformed the community and gave rise to organizational forms and institutions that continue to structure communal life today.

In addition to the barricades, another crucial strategy involved the lighting of approximately 240 *fogatas*—communal bonfires located throughout neighborhood intersections.¹⁴ Initially, the fogatas functioned as spaces of vigilance and self-defense organized at the neighborhood level. Families from different generations gathered around the fires twenty-four hours a day, sharing food while reactivating and reinventing the *ronda comunitaria*, a communal civil security body that had fallen into disuse by the late 1970s.¹⁵

The conversations shared around the fires also reactivated collective memories that became essential for imagining how to transform the trauma of violence and environmental destruction into an autonomous political project. Through dialogue within the fogatas, residents gradually revived older forms of political organization that had previously fallen into disuse.¹⁶ The position of fogata coordinator was established as a territorial representative responsible for convening neighbors, communicating community decisions, and organizing collective tasks. The organization around the fogatas also revitalized the four neighborhood assemblies and the General Assembly as spaces for communal decision-making. As a result, the fogata became a fundamental space of democratic participation, collective responsibility, political formation, and communal self-determination.

The self-defense movement against illegal logging expanded over time and eventually intersected with the state electoral calendar. In this context, both within the fogatas and

¹⁴ Jurhamuti Velázquez y Luz Lepe, “Parankuecha, diálogos y aprendizajes: Las fogatas de Cherán como praxis educativa comunitaria”, in *International Journal of Multicultural Education*, vol. 15, no. 3, 2013.

¹⁵ Alicia Lemus, “Educación Comunitaria: la Ronda Tradicional en Cherán, Michoacán”, in Rocio Moreno (coord.), *Cherán K’eri: Xanaruecha engajtsini miatántajka juchaari jurhéntperakuani. Cherán K’eri: Caminos para recordar nuestra educación*, Gobierno Comunal de Cherán y Universidad de Guadalajara. Mexico, 2019.

¹⁶ Verónica Velázquez, *Reconstitución del Territorio Comunal: El movimiento autonómico étnico en San Francisco Cherán, Michoacán*, master’s thesis (unpublished), CIESAS, Mexico, 2013.

the communal assemblies, the community decided not to participate in that year's elections through the official political party system. Instead, it was considered essential to exercise the right to elect authorities according to their own customary norms and practices, as well as to govern themselves through a municipal self-government structure grounded in their cultural practices. In February 2012, the “uprising” culminated in the establishment of a communal self-government, recognized as an exercise of the Right to Self-Determination through a ruling issued by the Electoral Tribunal of the Federal Judiciary.¹⁷

The first structure of the Communal Government was composed of a Major Council of Communal Government (CMGC), consisting of eleven male comuneros and one female comunera, replacing the position of municipal president. This body was supported by six operational councils responsible for governmental and administrative functions. During the 2012–2015 administration, the operational councils included: Communal Lands, Civil Affairs, Justice Administration, Surveillance and Mediation, Neighborhood Coordination, Local Administration, and Social, Economic, and Cultural Programs. Beginning with the second term of communal government (2015–2018), two additional councils were incorporated: Women and Youth. Each member of the governmental structure is elected through open voting by the assemblies of the four neighborhoods that make up the municipal seat of Cherán, and their appointments are subsequently ratified by the General Assembly. The Neighborhood Assemblies and the General Assembly constitute the highest authorities.

This communal government was accompanied by the reestablishment of a reinvented *ronda comunitaria* (community patrol), which has provided territorial and public security for the inhabitants. In addition to internal patrols, the ronda permanently installed checkpoints at the entrances to the town, which during the uprising had functioned as

¹⁷ Orlando Aragón, *El Derecho En Insurrección. Hacia Una Antropología Jurídica Militante Desde La Experiencia de Cherán, México*, Ciudad de México: Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México. México, 2019.

barricades to prevent the incursion of armed illegal loggers. Likewise, although the use of the fogata as a mechanism of surveillance was no longer necessary, the position of fogata coordinator has remained in place. In the present, there are 188 fogatas, and the coordinator is responsible for communicating the decisions made by the residents of each block during neighborhood assemblies and for organizing and delegating communal tasks.¹⁸

Through this self-government structure, the comuneros and comuneras of Cherán challenge mechanisms of resource dispossession and territorial appropriation, violence, states of exception, the collusion between municipal, state, and federal governments and organized crime, as well as the electoral system and the political party structure itself.

Collective rights and the uses of law in Cherán

In the more recent context of the incorporation of Human Rights into Latin American constitutions and the adoption of the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples, the year 2012 marked the first case in Mexico in which an Indigenous autonomy was formally recognized through judicial means in favor of the community of Cherán. This ruling proved paradigmatic because it not only recognized that elections would be conducted according to “usos y costumbres” (customary norms and practices)—a framework that had already been legislated in states such as Oaxaca—but also established that the government itself would operate according to the community’s own normative system.¹⁹

This allowed the community to establish its own governmental structure, as described in the previous section, while obligating the Mexican state to respect this structure and implement the necessary adaptations within its legal and institutional frameworks. Although several of these adaptations remain pending, and the community itself has had

¹⁸ Jurhamuti Velázquez y Luz Lepe, “Parankuecha, diálogos y aprendizajes... cit.”

¹⁹ Orlando Aragón, *El Derecho En Insurrección...* cit.

to adjust in order to facilitate its interaction with state institutions, the ruling nevertheless opened a legal and political framework that enabled other Indigenous communities to pursue judicial avenues in order to exercise their rights to self-determination, autonomy, and collective rights.

The struggle for autonomy in Cherán was triggered by the defense of the communal forest against illegal logging, which by 2011 had devastated 71% of the forest area compared to its extent in 2006.²⁰ It is important to emphasize that this was not merely illegal logging in a formal sense, but rather a form of massive and openly tolerated extraction that reached such proportions precisely because it had been instrumentalized by organized crime, whose power enabled collusion with local governments and produced a kind of “absent state.” Violence was also pervasive throughout other dimensions of community life.

For this reason, the struggle in Cherán articulated the defense of both the forest and the community itself. It is important to note the contrast between this context and the community’s response, which ultimately culminated in the formal legal recognition of autonomy. It was the community itself, through the exercise of autonomy in practice, that enabled the transition between these two poles.

Autonomy can only be understood through the concrete conditions of its exercise. As a result, autonomy takes different forms, experiences, and degrees of scope.²¹ As María de Jesús Patricio explains: “autonomy is expressed at many levels and in many forms... it is expressed in many levels because there are many Indigenous peoples here in Mexico, and each one has its own forms and its own ways of moving forward”.²²

Patricio identifies several forms of autonomy: (1) those exercised outside the structures of the state and without access to public budgets; (2) those that operate within state

²⁰ María España-Boquera y Omar Champo-Jiménez, “Proceso de deforestación en el Municipio de Cherán, Michoacán, México (2006-2012)”, in *Madera y Bosques*, vol. 22, no. 1, 2016.

²¹ Marco Aparicio, "El derecho de los Pueblos..." cit., p. 411.

²² María de Jesús Patricio, “El Sexto Panel Organizado por la Red de Comunicación Indígena Internacional (RCII)”, available at <https://www.facebook.com/watch/?v=2612853165638485> [last accessed: septiembre 2, 2020].

structures and exercise control over public resources; (3) those that emerge in response to security problems and establish their own security bodies; and (4) those grounded in the practice of traditional medicine—“placing healthcare in the hands of the communities”—which emphasize the protection of land and the care of territory, and which are present in many Indigenous communities.²³

III. Community Care and Collective Responses to the Pandemic

In Mexico, confinement as a preventive measure against Covid-19 was implemented nationwide beginning on March 23, 2020. Federal public health policy avoided imposing mandatory lockdowns, taking into consideration both the context of violence and the country’s socioeconomic conditions, given that more than half of the population works within the informal economy. Nevertheless, state governments adopted their own public health strategies, and some implemented mandatory confinement measures that, in certain cases, resulted in abuses of power by police forces.²⁴

In response to this uncertainty, some rural communities implemented their own confinement measures based on local histories and preexisting forms of community organization related to security and territorial defense.²⁵ These measures appeared recurrently in communities with strong communal organizational structures and Indigenous populations, with the aim of mitigating the spread of contagion in contexts where healthcare infrastructure is limited and where the population faces structural barriers to accessing medical services.²⁶

²³ Ídem

²⁴Subsecretaría de Derechos Humanos, Población y Migración, *Observaciones sobre Violaciones a Derechos Humanos durante la Contingencia Sanitaria por COVID-19*. 2020, available at <<https://www.gob.mx/conavim/documentos/observaciones-sobre-violaciones-a-derechos-humanos-durante-la-contingencia-sanitaria-por-covid-19-241321>> [last accessed: septiembre 2, 2020].

²⁵ Restrictive mobility measures were implemented in 340 municipalities across 15 states during the first days of confinement, according to the Subsecretaría de Derechos Humanos, Población y Migración. Ídem.

²⁶ Magdalena Gómez “Autodefensa de pueblos indígenas ante la pandemia”, *La Jornada*, April 14, 2020, available at <https://www.jornada.com.mx/2020/04/14/opinion/017a1pol> [last accessed: April 14, 2020].

In localities with community-based security organizations such as *rondas comunitarias* or community police forces, these groups were often responsible for implementing such measures through the installation of health checkpoints, as occurred in several towns affiliated with the Regional Coordinator of Community Authorities–Community Police (CRAC-PC)²⁷ and the Union of Peoples and Organizations of the State of Guerrero (UPOEG),²⁸ in Guerrero; as well as with the Ronda Comunitaria of Cherán in Michoacán. These strategies have been questioned and have generated conflicts with municipal authorities in various Indigenous communities and towns throughout the country, although this was not the case in Cherán. The pandemic response guidelines issued by the United Nations, the Inter-American Commission, and the Inter-American Court coincide in recognizing that these confinement measures constitute justified actions and form part of the collective rights of Indigenous peoples.²⁹

Cherán responses to Covid-19

The population of Cherán, like that of many Indigenous communities, faced significant risks in the event of the spread of Covid-19. More than half of the population experiences high levels of marginalization, and 28.13% lives in conditions of extreme poverty.³⁰ Regarding public health, chronic illnesses such as hypertension, diabetes, and obesity are common among adults between twenty-two and seventy years old.³¹ Medical infrastructure consists of one regional hospital and two rural health clinics.

²⁷ Arturo de Dios Palma, “Policía Comunitaria en Guerrero toma las armas contra el Covid-19”, *El Universal*, available at <<https://www.eluniversal.com.mx/estados/policia-comunitaria-en-gue-rrero-toma-las-armas-contra-el-covid-19/>> [last accessed: May 8, 2020].

²⁸ Quadratín, “Armados impiden a turistas entrar a la Costa Chica por coronavirus”, *Quadratín Guerrero*, April 12, 2020, available at <<https://guerrero.quadratín.com.mx/armados-impiden-a-turistas-en-trar-a-la-costa-chica-por-coronavirus/>> [last accessed: May 8, 2020].

²⁹ Inter-American Commission on Human Rights, Resolution 1/2020.

³⁰ SEDESOL, *Catálogo de Localidades*, available at <http://www.microrregiones.gob.mx/catloc/LocdeMun.aspx?tipo=clave&campo=loc&ent=16&mun=024> [last accessed: April 10, 2020].

³¹ Alicia Lemus, Juan Jerónimo y Fernando Jerónimo, “Autonomía Indígena: la crisis pandémica y las respuestas comunitarias en Cherán K’eri”, in *Ichan Tecolotl: La casa del tecolote*, available at <https://ichan.ciesas.edu.mx/covid-19-autonomia-indigena-la-crisis-pandemica-y-las-respuestas-comunitarias-en-cheran-keri/> [last accessed: April 10, 2020].

Knowing this, the community developed a rapid response to the health crisis triggered by Covid-19, although not without internal debates and disagreements. Many of the communal measures were coordinated and implemented in collaboration with the government of the state of Michoacán. On March 17, members of the Major Council and the person responsible for the Public Health Commission met with the state Secretary of Government, as well as with municipal presidents and health delegates, in order to establish a public health action plan focused primarily on disseminating preventive measures.

These agreements were subsequently discussed within the assemblies of Cherán's four neighborhoods, where it was decided to suspend all activities and events involving large public gatherings, including the celebration of the anniversary of the uprising on April 15, as well as the assemblies themselves. Subsequently, it was agreed to strengthen the Public Health Commission through the incorporation of a technical team composed of a pharmaceutical biochemist, a psychologist, and an administrative assistant. Most of the actions undertaken by the communal government structure during the pandemic were led by this technical team.

Preventive measures were disseminated through murals and posters placed throughout the community, as well as through mobile loudspeaker announcements that circulated across the four neighborhoods. In addition, the programming of the community radio station, Radio Fogata, continuously broadcast information related to the pandemic. Likewise, nurses and healthcare personnel organized itinerant workshops on sanitary measures and public health education.

As part of the community care measures, public funds were used to produce liquid soap, hand sanitizer, and face masks, which were distributed to people over the age of sixty-five and to those suffering from chronic illnesses. Recurring sanitation measures were implemented in the town square and the municipal market; distancing lines were painted on the ground in crowded areas; and informal vendors were relocated in order to avoid

the concentration of people. In anticipation of possible Covid-19 cases within the community, the Public Health Commission created a WhatsApp group connecting personnel from medical offices and healthcare units.

At the same time, young members of the community pursuing studies in health-related fields established health checkpoints at the barricades to provide guidance regarding preventive measures and identify possible carriers of the virus. As a support strategy for vulnerable populations, the Major Council purchased and distributed basic food products for sale in each neighborhood; local teachers organized fundraising efforts to purchase food supplies; and the Council of Social Programs, together with the fogata coordinators, distributed food packages free of charge through a program funded by the state government.

Following the confirmation of Covid-19 cases in Paracho, a neighboring municipality, on April 13 the Major Council issued a public statement requesting that migrants residing in the United States refrain from returning to Cherán or, alternatively, comply with sanitary isolation measures upon arrival. The Council also implemented a curfew, understood as the “prohibition or restriction on freely circulating through the streets of a city and/or remaining in public spaces, requiring inhabitants to remain in their homes except in cases of necessity or emergency”.³²

In addition, the statement urged residents to comply with preventive measures that had already appeared in previous communiqués and that coincided with the broader national public health strategy: staying at home, washing hands frequently, maintaining physical distance, wearing face masks, and avoiding gatherings. Enforcement of the curfew was entrusted to the Ronda Comunitaria. In cases of noncompliance with mobility restrictions, individuals would first receive a warning and, subsequently, could be assigned community work in support of the measures implemented during the public health

³² CMGC_2018-2021, “Comunicado del Concejo Mayor del 26 de abril del 2020”, available at <<https://www.facebook.com/photo?fbid=285665359111972&set=a.113659689645874> [last accessed: August 12, 2020].

emergency.

According to the head of the Public Health Commission, between 80 and 90 percent of the population complied with the recommendation to remain at home. The remaining 10 percent consisted primarily of street vendors, for whom suspending economic activities threatened their day-to-day subsistence.

In the first months of the pandemic, authorities in Paracho restricted access for vendors to the informal Sunday market, which usually attracted hundreds of buyers from neighboring communities. Since informal vendors depended on daily income and could not rely on financial savings, they organized an itinerant market throughout the streets of Cherán, thereby transgressing the agreement established by the neighborhood assemblies prohibiting commercial activity.

This situation reflected a tension between economic survival and public health that the pandemic exposed globally. Nevertheless, this lack of compliance did not produce coercive measures, although it became part of the broader debate expressed through official community networks. As the head of the Public Health Commission explained, “we cannot impose authoritarianism”.³³

During the first three months following the declaration of confinement measures, prevention strategies were firmly oriented toward keeping Cherán free of Covid-19 cases. However, this objective proved difficult to achieve because the community functions as a commercial and service center for surrounding towns.

Merchants from other P’urhépecha communities regularly travel to Cherán to purchase goods and supplies. Likewise, the local office of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs receives significant numbers of people seeking passport services or assistance regarding relatives residing in the United States. Due to the lack of certain services in neighboring localities, many residents travel to Cherán in order to receive medical care in clinics, purchase

³³ Interview conducted on May 15, 2020.

medications, send packages and telegrams, or collect remittances from banks.

To this circulation of local and outside visitors was added the growing number of coronavirus cases in communities surrounding Cherán. Eventually, the population relaxed isolation and physical distancing measures. Under these circumstances, and quite understandably, the aspiration of maintaining a “Covid-free Cherán” ultimately collapsed. On June 14, state authorities confirmed the first hospitalized coronavirus case within the community. By mid-July, the first deaths had been reported. Fear of contagion generated intense social tension within the population, to the point that infected individuals and their families became stigmatized.

Among the families facing this stigmatization, one *comunero*, while grieving the death of his father from Covid-19, confronted the atmosphere of fear and stress by publicly sharing his mourning process and clinical experience on Facebook. Through several images, he showed the altar prepared to bid farewell to his father—given the impossibility of organizing a traditional wake—the symptoms he experienced during the illness, and the herbal remedies through which he recovered from the infection. He recommended steam inhalations and infusions combining bay laurel (*Laurus nobilis*), chamomile (*Matricaria chamomilla*), and nurity (*Satureja macrostema*) in order to open the respiratory tract, as well as prayers to divine power asking for spiritual peace for each infected person.

Although the symptoms of the virus varied from person to person, this *comunero* approached the illness with a strong sense of social responsibility, sharing his experience in the hope that it might help others. It is worth noting that, following criticisms from members of the Public Health Commission regarding the scientific basis of these natural remedies, some of the recordings were removed from social media.

At the same time that the number of infected families within the community continued to increase, the Public Health Commission intensified its strategies in order to eradicate chains of transmission while allowing economic activities to continue. In mid-July, ten young people with training in clinical health were incorporated as health inspectors. These

“guardians of health,” dressed in white coats, face shields, and masks, monitored formal and informal businesses to ensure the proper implementation of preventive measures during interactions between customers and vendors. Their supervision also extended to health checkpoints established in the community’s most frequented spaces, including banks, the cultural center where the operational councils hold meetings, the locations where food packages and financial assistance from social programs are distributed, the urban planning offices, and the Council of Honor and Justice.

The sanitization of spaces and people became one of the principal strategies implemented by the Public Health Commission. Sanitization campaigns were carried out constantly in the main streets, public squares, walkways, markets, banks, and in the Cherán hospital, which attended patients infected with coronavirus. Some schools were also periodically sanitized when families visited to complete school admission procedures. Likewise, a local store was established to provide protective and disinfectant supplies manufactured within the community and sold at lower prices than those available on the commercial market.

In addition to these hygiene measures, the Public Health Commission sought to keep the community continuously informed. Through social media, it shared daily statistical data regarding the number of tested, confirmed, suspected, negative, recovered, and deceased Covid-19 cases at both the state and local levels. The Commission also created graphs, maps, and a mobile application for Android devices that tracked the evolution of Covid-19 using data provided by the state health system, the National Council of Science and Technology (CONACYT), and the regional hospital.

The prevention strategies implemented by the communal government structure were coordinated with state authorities, however, decision-making within Cherán continued to rely on the organization of the fogata. The fogata coordinator serves as a representative before the neighborhood assembly, and during the pandemic these coordinators became responsible for communicating and organizing community healthcare strategies among

the families living within each city block. In this sense, the fogata became yet another cell of deliberation and community democracy.

It is possible to observe that the discourse articulating these public health measures was closely connected to the imaginary of the autonomy movement and territorial defense, as well as to the functioning of communal institutions such as the ronda comunitaria. The strategy deployed to prevent contagion relied upon preexisting forms of community organization that had previously been developed to provide security and territorial defense. These organizational forms possess deeper historical roots and have evolved through the exercise of self-determination, particularly through the community's appropriation of security functions in response to external threats such as illegal logging, within a context characterized by state omission or permissiveness.

The articulation of pandemic measures with this broader political and communal discourse may have contributed to the effectiveness of the strategies implemented, as well as to the emergence of a response involving multiple sectors of the community rather than being limited solely to formal authorities.

At the same time, the social rejection directed toward certain residents infected with Covid-19 may be interpreted from several perspectives. First, it reflects the deficiencies of a healthcare system incapable of guaranteeing adequate medical attention. Second, it expresses uncertainty regarding the possible severity of the disease, which could range from asymptomatic cases to severe illness or death. Finally, the climate of social, labor, and economic insecurity generated by the pandemic situated the potentially infected person within a securitarian logic of infiltration, in which the individual could come to be perceived as an internal threat to the community.³⁴

³⁴ In several towns in Michoacán, checkpoints and barricades were established as a means of defending communities against the advance of organized crime, allowing for the regulation of dangerous situations. Under the context of Covid-19, these checkpoints were transformed into sanitary filters, such that the same apparatus of security regulation was repurposed for the detection and containment of biological danger. Unlike their previous use in preventing the infiltration of criminal groups into the towns, health checkpoints operated largely through an abstract form of protection, since they were deployed against an “invisible enemy” of which anyone

Thus far, this article has described some of the community strategies developed in response to the pandemic through the communal government structure, particularly those that became most visible through social media and official statements. However, our research into the use of traditional medicine within the community also led us toward less visible, though equally important, organized practices carried out by a group of women centered on therapeutic work with medicinal plants and midwifery.

Casa de la Mujer Indígena and the use of traditional healthcare during the pandemic

In addition to the strategies implemented by the Public Health Commission, women from the Casa de la Mujer Indígena (CAMI-Cherán) organized complementary initiatives aimed at addressing and preventing the pandemic. Their work characteristically focuses on the reproduction and care of individual, family, and community life, as well as on supporting women who are victims of domestic, sexual, physical, psychological, and/or economic violence.

The Casa de la Mujer in Cherán, known in the P'urhépecha language as *uarimas kuajpiricha anapuecha*, was founded in 2016 with financial support from the Major Council (2015–2018) and training provided by the National Commission for the Development of Indigenous Peoples (CDI). At the national level, this project began in 2003 as part of the neo-Indigenist institutional framework.³⁵ Institutional support, however, has not determined the operation of the 35 Casas de la Mujer Indígena y Afromexicana (CAMIs) established throughout the country. Indigenous and Afro-Mexican women have appropriated this initiative and transformed these houses into community spaces dedicated to counseling, support, and care for women, particularly in rural regions where institutional presence has historically been limited and deficient.³⁶

could potentially be a carrier. It was therefore no coincidence that war metaphors were frequently used to describe these forms of sanitary control.

³⁵ Aida Hernández, Sarela Paz y Teresa Sierra, *El Estado y los indígenas en tiempos del PAN: neoindigenismo, legalidad e identidad*, H. Cámara de Diputados, LIX Legislatura, CIESAS, Miguel Ángel Porrúa. México, 2004.

³⁶ Aida Hernández, “Casa de la Mujer Indígena: proyectos que salvan vidas” en *La Jornada*. 8 de mayo de 2020, available at <<https://www.jornada.com.mx/2020/05/08/opinion/018a1pol>> [last accessed: August 12, 2020].

The CAMI in Cherán was founded by ten women between the ages of twenty-six and sixty, each bringing different forms of knowledge, abilities, and experience, and all concerned with women's health and well-being, the defense of symbolic territoriality, and the preservation of ancestral knowledge related to natural remedies and midwifery. The prestige and recognition of this space are grounded in women who have worked as midwives, nurses, and healers for more than thirty years; to this experience is added the fact that these forms of knowledge and practice were passed down to them by their mothers and grandmothers. These women are also recognized for decades of commitment to community work, to the defense and care of the forest, and to safeguarding the medicinal knowledge derived from the forest within which local life unfolds.

The CAMI is not formally part of the communal government structure. In Cherán, however, its strategies for defending Indigenous women's rights are coordinated with various commissions and operational councils. For example, when a woman approaches the project after experiencing physical violence from her partner, the case is referred to the Council of Honor and Justice for follow-up. This coordination also operates in the opposite direction: mothers who approach the Women's Council because of health-related or psychological problems are referred to the CAMI for care and support.

As a result of the pandemic, the original caregiving, reproductive, and support tasks carried out by the project have intensified significantly. Demand expanded to other women, who joined the founding group in order to help build a more comprehensive community health system. Family members of patients now come to the space seeking natural remedies and medicinal plants to treat mild bodily symptoms associated with Covid-19, as well as other forms of physical and emotional exhaustion produced by voluntary isolation.

In this context, members of the CAMI observed an increase in women experiencing depression, stress, anxiety, headaches, insomnia, and skin conditions. These effects on physical, mental, and emotional health are addressed through three complementary approaches. First, through the preparation and distribution of herbal infusions, spiritual cleansings, ointments, oils, soaps, and extracts made from plants cultivated in household gardens or gathered from the forest meadows. Second, through therapeutic and relaxation massages. Finally, through techniques drawn from clinical psychology.

The demand for care, follow-up, and support for pregnant women has also increased in Cherán and in the neighboring communities served by the project. Adela Fabián, the midwife who forms part of the team, interprets this increased demand as a response to the fear of becoming infected with coronavirus in public clinics. Consequently, Adela, together with Guadalupe Ramos, another midwife, and the traditional healer Berta Ortiz, conduct house-to-house visits in order to provide prenatal and postnatal care and to look after newborn children.

For these comuneras, the concern for safeguarding community health also expanded into other technological and communicative spaces. Through the radio station XEPUR (“The Voice of the P’urhépecha People”), the women provide weekly advice on strategies to mitigate the psychological effects of confinement on families; offer legal and emotional support to women subjected to physical violence; and recommend foods and medicinal plants that strengthen the immune system and improve blood circulation.³⁷

The women of the CAMI consider the practices and knowledge of clinical medicine indispensable for the recovery of people affected by Covid-19. They support the efforts of local health authorities in disseminating preventive measures and collaborate with doctors from local clinics in the treatment of patients hospitalized because of coronavirus and other illnesses. They recognize herbal medicine as a complement to the allopathic medications recommended for treating these conditions. In contrast, members of the Public Health Commission have questioned the scientific basis of these women’s phytotherapeutic practices in treating the symptoms associated with the new coronavirus.

The founding group of the house positions itself with remarkable strength in the face of the pandemic, expressing neither complaints nor despair regarding the shortage of medicines and medical supplies available in the hospital for treating those who become ill: “there is no need to fear this virus, because it has existed before,” they affirm.³⁸ They

³⁷ Chamomile (*Matricaria chamomilla*), nurié (*Satureja macrostema*), dandelion (*Taraxacum officinale*), and rosemary (*Rosmarinus officinalis*) are among the herbs most commonly recommended to those seeking relief from mild symptoms associated with the novel coronavirus. These remedies are administered as herbal infusions, tinctures, microdoses, or through bathing the body with preparations made from these plants, typically in uninterrupted treatments lasting nine days.

³⁸ Interview conducted on June 22, 2020.

appeal to communal memory, recalling how previous pandemics throughout the twentieth and twenty-first centuries—such as the Spanish flu, measles, and influenza—were confronted and overcome.

They recognize that ancestral knowledge used to address these illnesses operated simultaneously upon the individual body and the social body, weaving together the materiality of the physical body, the territory, and nature as the primary source of health and healing. Among these healing practices, they recall that their ancestors prescribed the regular consumption of medicinal plants on an individual basis and the use of natural remedies such as *temazcales*.³⁹ At the collective level, they organized dances, ceremonies, and rituals carried out in sacred metonymic spaces located at the heart of the community's symbolic territoriality.⁴⁰ These practices are remembered as effective because, although such diseases devastated the population, Cherán ultimately repopulated and endured.

Like many other Indigenous communities and peoples throughout Latin America, the territory itself has functioned as another space of healing during the pandemic.⁴¹ Both CAMI comuneras and other community members have entered the forest to organize *temazcales* that invoke ancestral memories of health and healing.⁴² The *temazcal* refers to healing through coexistence and balance between human beings and nature. It draws upon

³⁹ The *temazcal* is a pre-Hispanic therapeutic steam bath traditionally used to close the womb and to cleanse women physically and symbolically after childbirth. The term derives from the Nahuatl words *temas* (steam) and *calli* (house).

⁴⁰ Alicia Barabas, “La construcción de etnoterritorios...” cit. p. 85-107.

⁴¹ Letti Viteri, “El Sumak Kausai frente al Covid-19”, en *Debates Indígenas*. Available at <<https://debatesindigenas.org/notas/52-sumak-kausai-covid-19.html>>. [last accessed: September 5, 2020].

⁴² In the forest, community members gather branches and weave them into a rounded structure resembling an igloo. Before construction begins, offerings are made to Mother Earth (*nana echari*)—such as copal, incense, corn, candles, and flowers—in order to ask permission to occupy that space. Once the dome-shaped framework is secured, it is covered with blankets, leaving only a small entrance. At the same time, volcanic stones known as the “grandmothers” are heated for several hours. Once the grandmothers are glowing red-hot, participants enter the dome and sit along its inner walls. The healing bath begins when the person guiding the *temazcal* requests that a specific number of heated stones be placed at the center of the enclosure and the entrance is closed. Within the darkened space, fresh bundles of medicinal plants are distributed among the participants. The healer leading the ceremony pours water over the heated stones, producing steam that causes the participants to sweat, detoxify, and open their respiratory passages. With eyes closed, in silence, and breathing slowly and deeply, participants are encouraged to become conscious of the ailments affecting them while gently brushing the branches across their bodies in order to stimulate blood circulation and loosen phlegm. A *temazcal* ceremony may last between forty-five minutes and an hour and a half. During this time, the entrance is opened four times. Each opening allows fresh air to enter and additional heated stones to be introduced, gradually intensifying the heat and thickening the steam. On some occasions, the guides of the *temazcal* perform songs or prayers intended to call upon the beings inhabiting the cosmos to assist in the healing of the sick person.

a feminine energy of healing: its circular form symbolizes a return to the mother's womb and invites rebirth. In both a physical and spiritual sense, it calls upon the grandmothers (the stones) and *nana echari* (Mother Earth) to purify and cleanse those who participate.

Traditional healers and midwives act as caretakers of the balance between community health, human bodies, the environment, the land, and the territory in its cultural, symbolic, and historical dimensions. They possess highly specialized knowledge concerning local flora, cosmogony, and the relationship between land-territory and bodily care and healing.⁴³ In the patios and backyard gardens of their homes, they cultivate and harvest some of the medicinal plants they use as remedies, and through their work they contribute to the preservation of local flora and biodiversity.⁴⁴

The work carried out by the CAMIs has become especially significant in the context of confinement policies, in which domestic labor, childcare, and the care of the sick and the elderly have been disproportionately placed upon women, as though such responsibilities were somehow essential to femininity; while at the same time various forms of gender violence have intensified upon women's bodies. In the face of global priorities centered on projects of land and territorial dispossession, the work carried out by the women of the CAMI forms part of the broader struggle for territorial defense and for the preservation of communal life. The politics of care they promote intertwines the protection of community life, individual bodily health, cultural systems, territory, and nature. Yet when this network of care is combined with the struggle to eradicate gender violence, it also gives political consistency and depth to the mobilization of Cherán.

In the words of Lorena Cabnal: "In defending the territory-land, women carry out an extraordinary everyday and parallel defense in two inseparable dimensions: the defense of

⁴³ The gathering and transformation of plants into medicinal remedies involves highly specialized forms of knowledge. Each plant must be collected on specific days of the week, at particular times of day or night, and according to the specific part of the plant to be used. This body of knowledge governing medical practice emerges from a complex relationship between the natural environment and culture, within a human-nature symbiosis that "derives from an accurate understanding of the pharmacological properties of plants, which today provide sufficient foundations for their curative purposes." See Juan Gallardo, *Medicina tradicional p'urhépecha...* op. cit., p. 131.

⁴⁴ Paulina Trejo, "Guardianes del corazón de la tierra", in Leyva Xochitl y Rosalva Icaza (cords.), *En tiempos de muerte: cuerpos, rebeldías, resistencias*, Cooperativa editorial retos, CLACSO y Erasmus University Rotterdam, Argentina, México y Países Bajos, 2019.

our body-territory and the defense of our land-territory”.⁴⁵ If the mobilization of Cherán was and continues to be a struggle for life, then caring for the personal integrity of each inhabitant and defending the land-territory represent vital spaces of resistance and political coherence.

Among the women who form part of the CAMI is Doña Chepa, known as “the guardian of the forest.” She also was among the women who initiated the community mobilization in defense of the forest on April 15, 2011. On that day, they placed their bodies as the first territory of defense against the illegal loggers. When Doña Chepa was asked what motivated her to confront the illegal loggers, she explained that she felt “great anger and sadness” over the destruction of the century-old pine trees surrounding the sacred spring of the *cofradía* by armed men. This amalgam of emotions can be understood through the particular relationship that women maintain with the territory. Women are the ones who enter the forest in search of mushrooms and the flora that supplements family nutrition; under their care also remain some of the markers of symbolic and sacred ethnoterritoriality, such as springs, hills, stone mounds, and caves.

These forms of knowledge and care were threatened by the climate of insecurity imposed by logging entrepreneurs and organized crime. Added to this relationship with the ethnoterritory was the threat directed toward women’s own bodies: “Once we finish off the forest, we’ll take your women,” the loggers used to say.⁴⁶ In other words, women’s bodies continued to function as fields of dispute and appropriation within struggles over territorial control.

Doña Chepa’s concern for defending and caring for the forest led her to hold a position within the Council of Communal Lands during the first communal government administration (2012–2015), a space that prior to the movement had been exclusively dominated by men. Through this process, Doña Chepa became increasingly politicized,

⁴⁵ Lorena Cabnal, “El relato de las violencias desde mi territorio cuerpo-tierra”, in Leyva Xochitl y Rosalva Icaza (cords.), *En tiempos de muerte: cuerpos, rebeldías, resistencias*, Cooperativa editorial retos, CLACSO y Erasmus University Rotterdam. Argentina, México y Países Bajos, 2019, p. 121.

⁴⁶ Fogata Kejtsitani, “¡Nuestra lucha es por la vida!”, available at <<https://kejtsitani.wordpress.com/2018/02/15/nuestra-lucha-es-por-lavida/>>. [last accessed: September 15, 2020]

eventually positioning herself within “the discourse of women’s rights, while continuing to connect it to the communal struggle”.⁴⁷ Along this path, she promoted the creation of the CAMI within the neighborhood assemblies.

The women who form part of the CAMI embody the intrinsic relationship between women and the care of land-territory; through this connection, they understand that defending the integrity of women constitutes an act of political coherence. They recognize that although the movement succeeded in eradicating much of the violence generated by organized crime, violence against women persists within the community itself.⁴⁸ Returning once again to the words of Lorena Cabnal, it is “a political and cosmogonic inconsistency to defend Mother Earth against neoliberalism while failing to defend the bodies of women and girls”.⁴⁹

In this sense, the work carried out by the women of CAMI-Cherán in defense of culture, land-territory, ancient religious and spiritual practices, herbal knowledge that enables reproductive self-determination, and women’s rights to bodily integrity and access to justice should be recognized at the same level as the communal government initiatives of Cherán aimed at self-management, territorial sovereignty, and community security.

CONCLUSIONS

Indigenous peoples and communities have resisted, confronted, and negotiated against governmental policies and development projects that have affected their forms of organization and territorial settlement. In recent decades, the implementation of the free-market model has represented a new assault on their territories through extractive projects and the intensification of resource exploitation carried out not only by transnational corporations and state initiatives, but also by criminal actors. Within this context, a new

⁴⁷ Verónica Velázquez, *Territorios Encarnados. Extractivismo, Comunalismos y Género en la Meseta P’urhépecha*, Universidad de Guadalajara, CIESAS, México, 2019, p. 242.

⁴⁸ See Verónica Velázquez, *Territorios Encarnados... cit.*

⁴⁹ Lorena Cabnal, “El relato de las violencias... cit.,” p. 122.

cycle of protest has emerged, organized around demands for collective rights and movements toward self-determination.

In the case presented here, the Indigenous community of Cherán defended its territory by confronting illegal logging and the political power of organized crime linked to official institutions. In doing so, the community deposed the municipal government structure, dissolved the police force, appropriated responsibility for security, and initiated the construction of a self-government based on customary norms and practices. The case of Cherán represents a struggle that articulated the defense of both the forest and the community itself.

Through this process, and unlike other experiences in Mexico, the community chose to create its own institutional structure, one that would allow a certain degree of articulation with state institutions while remaining centered on the protection and care of the community. This decision revealed important strengths, although it has not been free of tensions.

The population of Cherán, like that of many Indigenous communities, faced significant risks in the event of the spread of Covid-19. The community developed a rapid response to the health crisis triggered by Covid-19, although not without internal debates and disagreements. Many of the communal measures were coordinated and implemented in collaboration with the government of the state of Michoacán. Cherán developed a politics of care aimed at reducing the risks of contagion, grounded in its communal security structures and forms of self-government.

The politics of care has been immersed in both intracommunal and intercommunal social tensions. One area of tension has involved informal economic activities, while another source of concern has been the absence of measures aimed at addressing and preventing the damage that the pandemic will inevitably inflict upon the economic fabric of the community in the coming years.

As we have argued, the first responses implemented by Cherán's communal government structure were focused on confronting the public health emergency through forms of self-

isolation and communal enclosure, as had occurred during other moments of internal danger throughout the twentieth and twenty-first centuries. Confinement during the pandemic was accompanied by a hygienic and medical surveillance perimeter that oscillated between a commitment to the care of communal life and an appeal to individual responsibility for self-care.

Throughout the constant sanitization operations carried out in shared public spaces, communal authorities insisted that although these hygienic strategies contributed to interrupting chains of transmission, the principal responsibility ultimately rested on the adoption of preventive measures, personal hygiene, and self-care practices recommended by international health organizations. For their part, the familial and emotional ties that the population maintains with the health inspectors, encouraged the natural cooperation of individuals with these practices of sanitary monitoring and surveillance.

In complementarity with—and at times in tension with—the politics of care implemented by the communal government structure, the women of the CAMI confront the virus, which requires human bodies in order to reproduce and mutate, through forms of medicine provided by the land-territory and through bodies of knowledge forged across generations dedicated to the care and reproduction of nature and communal biological life.

Through their work of preserving and reproducing local flora, they address, in the long term, some of the most pressing consequences revealed by this public health crisis. Their labor should be recognized as a valuable practice of resistance against projects of territorial dispossession, as an expression of autonomy, and as an exercise in food and health sovereignty.

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